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Transitions between Large-Scale Vortices and Jets in Rotating Rayleigh-Bénard Convection

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Abstract

In this thesis, the transition between Large Scale Vortices (LSVs) and Jets in rotating Rayleigh-Bénard convection (RRBC) with a Prandtl number of 2.19 is investigated as domain anisotropy increases. Direct numerical simulations of the 3D complete set of RRBC equations were employed, where domain anisotropy was introduced by making one horizontal side of the computational domain longer than the other. The transition was analyzed by examining flow morphology and employing characteristic quantities that serve as analogs to the order parameter for this transition. Our findings reveal stable flow configurations that depend on the degree of anisotropy, including configurations with only LSVs, LSVs with banded jets, and only jets. Additionally, we observed the occurrence of a hysteresis loop near the transition between jets and LSVs. The transition from LSVs to jets exhibited features of a continuous transition, while the transition from jets to LSVs resembled a discontinuous transition.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background and Literature Review

Buoyancy-driven convective flows are widespread in nature, appearing in atmospheric flows, deep ocean currents, the liquid-metal outer core of Earth, giant gas planets, and the Sun [1]. For example, to model planetary core processes accurately, a solid understanding of turbulent core convection is crucial [2]. Although numerical simulations are the primary method for studying Earth and planetary dynamics, there is a significant gap between current numerical models and real planetary parameters, raising accuracy concerns [2]. Since dynamo simulations qualitatively resemble non-magnetic convection, rapidly rotating convection provides a simplified and effective model that captures essential core flow aspects [2].

The rotating Rayleigh–Bénard convection (RRBC) model is often used to investigate the complex interactions between buoyancy-driven turbulence and rotation, capturing the essential characteristics of the flow [1]. This model represents a layer of fluid between two horizontal plates, with the bottom plate at a higher temperature than the top plate, and rotating around a vertical axis aligned with gravity [1]. Key parameters of RRBC include the Rayleigh number (Ra) describing thermal forcing strength, the Ekman number (Ek) representing the relative importance of viscosity over rotation, and the Prandtl number (Pr) describing the diffusive properties of fluid [1]. Different flow regimes emerge depending on these parameters. For instance, with low thermal forcing and/or strong rotation, a “rotation-dominated” regime develops [3]. This regime is characterized by the dominant geostrophic balance, where the Coriolis force balances the pressure gradient forces [3]. Many geophysical and astrophysical convective flows are expected to fall under this regime [1]. In this regime, there are also several subregimes depending on the principal parameters. As thermal forcing increases, the flow transitions through the following regimes in order of increasing Ra : the cellular regime, the shielded convective Taylor columns (CTCs) regime, the plume regime, and finally the geostrophic turbulence (GT) regime [4]. The geostrophic turbulence is the regime within which the investigation of this study is aimed to be executed.

The geostrophic turbulence regime is characterized by intricate flow dynamics that differ significantly from typical 3D turbulent flows. A typical characteristic of 3D turbulence is a direct energy cascade that transports energy from larger macrostructures to intermediate-length scales and eventually to smaller microstructures, where kinetic energy dissipates due to viscous friction [5]. Conversely, the inherent feature of 2D turbulence is a partial inverse energy cascade carrying a fraction of kinetic energy from the injected scales toward large scales [6]. Interestingly, Taylor and Proudman demonstrated that for 3D turbulence under the strict geostrophic balance, the gradient of the velocity in the direction parallel to the rotation axis vanishes, indicating a quasi-two-dimensional (quasi-2D) behavior of the flow [3], [7]. This leads to an occurrence of the inverse energy cascade in the geostrophic turbulence regime [1]. As a consequence of this cascade, kinetic energy accumulates at the largest available length scale, forming domain-filling vertically coherent flow structures [3], [8].

The geostrophic turbulence regime of RRBC in the Cartesian square computational domain with

periodic boundary conditions has been widely investigated and has been shown to form a stable configuration consisting of a depth-invariant large-scale vortex (LSV), which grows to the horizontal box size [3], [8], [9]. Interestingly, the absence of LSVs in spherical models implies that large-scale dynamics prefer unidirectional flows over vortices, as seen in giant gas planets with zonal flows [8]. According to Rhines [10], variations in the Coriolis parameter due to latitude (known as the β -effect) influence flow dynamics by inhibiting the inverse energy cascade by scattering turbulent energy into wave energy, thereby promoting Rossby waves [10]–[12]. A distinctive feature of these waves is an association of large frequencies with large scales [10]. Rhines [10] posits that simultaneous energy transfer to smaller wavenumbers and lower frequencies is possible only when the energy flux is anisotropic and directed toward the zonal modes. Consequently, it is suggested that the β -effect breaks the horizontal isotropy of the flow field and promotes the formation of zonal jets [10], [12]. This concept was observed in a study of forced 2D turbulence by Maltrud and Valli [11], where increasing the β -effect initially weakened and eventually eliminated coherent vortices, leading to the emergence of unidirectional flows [11].

The Cartesian DNS domain matches convection near the poles where gravity aligns with the rotation axis, using flat boundaries, thereby omitting complexities like Rossby waves and zonal flows [2]. Intriguingly, it was observed that when anisotropy is introduced into the planar computational domain in the form of a rectangular domain with one horizontal side longer than the other, the large-scale structures formed include jets [8], [13]–[15]. This setup offers the opportunity to study certain aspects of jet dynamics within the Cartesian DNS, using periodic boundary conditions. Understanding jet dynamics is crucial, as zonal jets significantly impact planetary atmospheres, affecting atmospheric structure and predictability over various timescales [2]. Furthermore, jets are notably present in gas-giant planets like Jupiter and Saturn, but their detailed origin remains unclear [16], [17].

The emergence of jets in numerical simulations using a rectangular Cartesian domain with periodic boundary conditions has been explored by Guervilly and Hughes [8], Julien et al. [13], and Frishman et al. [14]. Guervilly and Hughes [8] used the full set of governing equations for 3D turbulence, Julien et al. [13] utilized reduced 3D equations, and Frishman et al. [14] focused on the forced 2D turbulence. Both Guervilly and Hughes [8] and Julien et al. [13] observed that introducing anisotropy through a non-square periodic domain caused a transition from configurations with only LSVs to those with both LSVs and jets. These jets formed parallel to the shorter horizontal dimension, with a characteristic scale comparable to the shortest side at a slight degree of anisotropy [8], [13]. Specifically, Guervilly and Hughes [8] found that jets coexisted with LSVs of a size comparable to the shortest side (L_x), while Julien et al. [13] observed vortical bands with persistent smaller vortical eddies separating jet-like flows. Similarly, Frishman et al. [14] have shown that at large scales, unidirectional flows and vortices coexist over long timescales, with jets embedding numerous vortices within an anisotropic turbulent background. Additionally, in Guervilly and Hughes [8] jets were first observed for the horizontal length ratio of $L_y/L_x \approx 1.08$ for $Pr = 1$, and similarly, Julien et al. [13] discovered that unidirectional jets with embedded persistent LSVs form when the horizontal length ratio L_y/L_x exceeds 1.1 for $Pr = 1$.

Additionally, near the transition from a configuration with only LSVs to one with jets, a bimodal

behavior was observed, where the system randomly switched between dipole vortex configurations and unidirectional flows for a specific range of L_y/L_x in the vicinity of transition [8], [15]. Bouchet and Simonnet [15], using 2D stochastic Navier-Stokes equations in the limit of weak forcing and dissipation, found bimodal behavior within the L_y/L_x range of 1.02 to 1.04. This phenomenon was not seen by Guervilly and Hughes [8] at an Ekman number of 10^{-5} . However, Bouchet and Simonnet [15] noted that such topological changes occur slowly over viscous time scales and that the solutions might depend on initial conditions and vary over long time scales. To investigate this further, Guervilly and Hughes [8] conducted simulations with an increased Ekman number ($Ek = 10^{-4}$), covering multiple viscous time scales. Within the range of $L_y/L_x \in [1.06, 1.15]$, they also observed bistability, where both the jet state and the LSV-only state could coexist [8].

Understanding the physical mechanisms underlying phase transitions is crucial because they involve significant changes in a system's qualitative properties due to minor adjustments in external parameters [18]. In the study of turbulence, the primary objective is to understand the statistical properties of the velocity field [18]. This might suggest using equilibrium statistical mechanics as a potential approach to address these problems [18]. However, in turbulence, the flow is generally not close to an equilibrium distribution due to the inherent energy dissipation [18]. Most turbulent flows are continuously driven by external forces and achieve a statistically steady state where the energy input from forcing is balanced by dissipation [18]. Such states are known in statistical mechanics as Non-Equilibrium Steady States (NESS) [18]. Due to the presence of energy fluxes in NESS, the microcanonical measure does not accurately describe their statistical characteristics [18]. Nevertheless, in the limit of weak forces and dissipation, the stationary measure might approximate the microcanonical equilibrium measure [18]. As in quasi-geostrophic turbulence forces and dissipation mechanisms are relatively weak compared to the inertial (Hamiltonian) dynamics [18], it is plausible that statistical equilibrium descriptions could provide insights into this non-equilibrium system.

The effects of horizontal domain anisotropy on flow behavior were analyzed analytically using equilibrium statistical mechanics by Bouchet and Venaille [18] for the 2D Navier-Stokes equations in a doubly periodic domain. This analysis indicated that two types of flow topologies can be expected: dipolar flows and parallel flows [18]. It was found that the equilibrium structure is significantly influenced by the geometry of the domain, particularly the ratio of the horizontal dimensions. The analysis predicted a transition from dipoles to parallel flows once the ratio of horizontal dimensions is 10% order [18]. These results show reasonable agreement between equilibrium statistical mechanics predictions and simulation results, suggesting that equilibrium statistical mechanics might be useful in describing this transition in flow configurations for the considered system. However, it was stressed by Bouchet and Venaille [18] that their equilibrium statistical mechanics approach cannot predict the main control parameters such as the probability of the energy or vorticity moments, but it is capable of giving some qualitative results. Therefore, in this study, the interpretation of the findings by drawing parallels with the equilibrium statistical mechanics framework is considered.

In statistical physics, the presence of two stable states near a transition for the same set of parameters

suggests the possibility of hysteresis behavior. This implies that the state realized by the system depends not only on the external parameters but also on the history of the system’s evolution. Hysteresis has been observed in RRBC during the transition from a direct energy cascade to an inverse energy cascade [3], [19]. Specifically, by Favier et al. [19] the bistability was reported during this transition at certain aspect ratios and Rayleigh numbers, and it was influenced by initial conditions. This transition was further examined by de Wit [3], where the occurrence of hysteresis when crossing the high-Rayleigh-number boundary of LSV stability was reported.

1.2 Research Question

The objective of this research is to examine the transition from a Large-Scale Vortex (LSV) configuration to jets within rotating Rayleigh-Bénard Convection simulated using the complete set of equations in a 3D Cartesian domain with doubly periodic boundary conditions in both horizontal directions. The study will specifically examine how this transition occurs as the ratio of horizontal dimensions, L_x/L_y , deviates from one for a Prandtl number of 2.19, a value relevant for liquids and not previously explored in this context, where only $Pr = 1$ is considered so far.

The findings will be interpreted by drawing parallels with the equilibrium statistical mechanics framework, as was outlined in section 1.1.

Specifically, the research aims to investigate the evolution of the stable coherent flow organization by analyzing the qualitative behavior of the flow and employing the concept of the order parameter, for the range L_x/L_y that is close to the transition region. It will also examine these configurations qualitatively. Additionally, the study will explore the occurrence of hysteresis during this transition.

1.3 Rotating Rayleigh-Bénard convection

In this section, the RRBC system used for the simulations is defined, the theoretical concepts underlying its flow dynamics are discussed, and the governing equations as well as their non-dimensional form are presented. Additionally, the quasi-2D behavior of the system in the limit of rapid rotation is demonstrated.

1.3.1 Defining the system

In this study, the rotating Reyleigh-Bénard convection is considered on a Cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z) with the respective unit vectors $(\hat{\mathbf{e}}_x, \hat{\mathbf{e}}_y, \hat{\mathbf{e}}_z)$. The coordinate frame is co-rotating with the system with angular velocity $\boldsymbol{\Omega} = \Omega \hat{\mathbf{e}}_z$ around the axis located at the center of the system. The rotational axis is aligned with the gravitational acceleration vector $-g \hat{\mathbf{e}}_z$, which is, consequently, termed as the vertical direction, while two other perpendicular directions are termed horizontal. The considered system is unbounded in the horizontal domain and bounded in the vertical domain, with a height H (condition 1). The upper and bottom planes are isothermal, with the bottom plane at a higher temperature T_h than the top one with temperature T_c (condition 2). The boundary conditions for the top and bottom planes of

the domain are stress-free (condition 3). The following boundary can be mathematically represented as follows:

$$w(z = 0, H) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$T(z = 0) = T_h, \quad T(z = H) = T_c \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial z}(z = 0, H) = 0, \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial z}(z = 0, H) = 0. \quad (3)$$

The developing convective flow is described by the following field quantities, which are functions of space and time t : velocity $\mathbf{u}(x, y, z, t) = u\hat{\mathbf{e}}_x + v\hat{\mathbf{e}}_y + w\hat{\mathbf{e}}_z$, temperature $T(x, y, z, t)$, and the pressure $P(x, y, z, t)$.

1.3.2 Governing equations

The principle of fluid motion is governed by the principles of mass, momentum, and energy conservation, which for the continuous flow are known as Navier-Stokes equations [20]. The basic form of these equations in the inertial frame for incompressible Newtonian flow with constant density, constant specific heat capacity c_p , and negligible heat production by viscous dissipation is as follows [5]:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{u} &= \mathbf{g} - \frac{1}{\rho}\nabla P + \nu\nabla^2\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{f} \\ \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla)T &= \kappa\nabla^2 T \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{f} is the acceleration due to other forces present in the fluid, ν is the kinematic viscosity, and κ is the thermal diffusivity of the fluid.

In this system, the Boussinesq approximation is used to account for buoyancy effects due to the density gradient caused by the temperature gradient across the fluid layer. This approximation assumes that the actual pressure, density, and temperature are close to a reference state and that the dependence of density on temperature can be linearized [5], [20]. Therefore, density ρ depends on temperature in the following way [3]:

$$\rho(T) = \rho_0(1 - \alpha_T(T - T_0)), \quad (5)$$

where ρ_0 and T_0 are the constant density and temperature of the fluid at static equilibrium, and α_T is the thermal expansion coefficient. According to this approximation, density variations and compressibility effects are neglected, except for the gravitational term, which is the driving term for convection [21]. The Boussinesq approximation is considered reasonable for convection when the product $\alpha_T(T - T_0) \leq 0.2$ [21].

To account for the fictitious forces in momentum conservation that arise from using a co-rotating coordinate system, the approach demonstrated in [7] is followed. First, the transformation rule between

reference frames for the derivative of the displacement vector \mathbf{r} with time (velocity) is considered:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{d\mathbf{r}}{dt}\right)_I &= \frac{d}{dt}(r_x\hat{\mathbf{e}}_x + r_y\hat{\mathbf{e}}_y + r_z\hat{\mathbf{e}}_z) = \\ \frac{dr_x}{dt}\hat{\mathbf{e}}_x + \frac{dr_y}{dt}\hat{\mathbf{e}}_y + \frac{dr_z}{dt}\hat{\mathbf{e}}_z + r_x\frac{d\hat{\mathbf{e}}_x}{dt} + r_y\frac{d\hat{\mathbf{e}}_y}{dt} + r_z\frac{d\hat{\mathbf{e}}_z}{dt} &= \\ \left(\frac{d\mathbf{r}}{dt}\right)_R + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r} & \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where subscript I denotes an inertial frame, and R denotes a rotational frame. Here the following transformation formula of the time derivatives of the unit vectors with respect to the inertial frame was used:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\hat{\mathbf{e}}_x}{dt} &= \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \hat{\mathbf{e}}_x \\ \frac{d\hat{\mathbf{e}}_y}{dt} &= \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \hat{\mathbf{e}}_y \\ \frac{d\hat{\mathbf{e}}_z}{dt} &= \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \hat{\mathbf{e}}_z \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The transformation rule 6 should be applied twice to compute the transformation formula for the second derivative of \mathbf{r} with time (acceleration). Consequently:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{d^2\mathbf{r}}{dt^2}\right)_I &= \frac{d}{dt} \left(\left(\frac{d\mathbf{r}}{dt}\right)_R + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r} \right) + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \left(\left(\frac{d\mathbf{r}}{dt}\right)_R + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r} \right) \\ &= \left(\frac{d^2\mathbf{r}}{dt^2}\right)_R + 2\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \left(\frac{d\mathbf{r}}{dt}\right)_R + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

In terms of acceleration, this formula can be written as follows:

$$\mathbf{a}_I = \mathbf{a}_R + 2\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{u}_R + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}) \quad (9)$$

In this way, in the non-inertial term, there are two contributions to the acceleration due to fictitious force: the Coriolis acceleration $2\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{u}_R$ and centrifugal acceleration $\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r})$ [7]. The latter term, as well as the gravitational contribution, can be written as a gradient, and incorporated into the pressure term, in the following way [3], [21]:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\Omega} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{r}) &= \Omega^2 \mathbf{r}_\perp = \nabla \left(\frac{1}{2} \Omega^2 r_\perp^2 \right) \\ \nabla p &= \nabla \left(P/\rho_0 + gz - \frac{1}{2} \Omega^2 r_\perp^2 \right) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where r_\perp is defined as projection of \mathbf{r} on the plane perpendicular to the rotation vector $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$, and p is a reduced pressure term [3], [21]. It is also important to note that when simulating systems with periodic boundary conditions, it is impractical to account for buoyancy effects resulting from centrifugal acceleration. This is because a particle moving outward from the rotation axis, upon reaching the boundaries of the computational domain, would re-enter the system from the opposite side with an

inwards moving direction, thereby unnaturally interfering with the system. Therefore, the buoyancy effects on the flow due to centrifugal acceleration are neglected in the governing equations that were used to simulate the system. Interestingly, it has been experimentally shown that it is reasonable to neglect the dynamical effects of buoyancy-driven flows due to centrifugal acceleration when the Froude number, which represents the significance of centrifugal effects relative to gravitational acceleration, satisfies the inequality $Fr = \frac{\Omega^2 R}{g} < 0.1$, where R is the distance to the rotation axis [3], [22].

Summing up, for the Newtonian fluid with incompressible flow in the rotational frame with angular velocity $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ with respect to the inertial frame, neglecting heat production by viscous dissipation, assuming constant c_p , and employing Boussinesq approximation, the governing equations for the studied system RRBC constitute the following set [3]:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\nabla} \cdot \mathbf{u} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \boldsymbol{\nabla})\mathbf{u} &= -\boldsymbol{\nabla}p + \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{g}\alpha(T - T_0)\hat{\mathbf{e}}_z - 2\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{R}} \\ \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \boldsymbol{\nabla})T &= \kappa \nabla^2 T \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Here the first equation represents the conservation of mass, known as the continuity equation. The second equation describes the conservation of momentum, and the third equation corresponds to the conservation of energy.

1.3.3 Quasi-2D flow in the rotation-dominated limit

In this section, the Taylor-Proudman theorem, which demonstrates quasi-2D behavior under rapid rotation, is presented according to the approach shown in [3].

For the geostrophic regime with rapid rotation, where the Coriolis term balances the pressure gradient, and significantly dominates over inertial, viscous, and buoyant terms [3], the following equality can be obtained:

$$2\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{u} = -\boldsymbol{\nabla}p \quad (12)$$

By taking the curl of this equality and using a vector identity for the left-hand side gives the following equality:

$$\boldsymbol{\nabla} \times (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \times \mathbf{u}) = (\mathbf{u} \cdot \boldsymbol{\nabla})\boldsymbol{\Omega} - (\boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \boldsymbol{\nabla})\mathbf{u} + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \boldsymbol{\nabla} \cdot \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u} \boldsymbol{\nabla} \cdot \boldsymbol{\Omega} = \mathbf{0} \quad (13)$$

By using the continuity equation $\boldsymbol{\nabla} \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$, and considering that $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ is constant, yields:

$$(\boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \boldsymbol{\nabla})\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0} \quad (14)$$

This equality shows that the gradient of the velocity in the direction aligned with the rotational vector is zero, indicating that any variations in the velocity field in the vertical direction vanish. Given the boundary conditions of zero vertical components of the velocity at the top and bottom planes, this leads

to a quasi-2D flow [3].

1.3.4 Non-dimensionalization of the governing equations

In this section, non-dimensionalization of the equations (11) is presented. The units used for non-dimensionalization are commonly referred to as convective units, for which the convenient velocity scale was found to be the free-fall velocity $U = \sqrt{g\alpha H\Delta T}$, which corresponds to the upper bound for the buoyancy-generated velocity [21]. Here $\Delta T = T_h - T_c$, and H is the characteristic length scale. Consequently, the dimensionless quantities are the following:

$$\tilde{x} = \frac{x}{H}, \quad \tilde{t} = \frac{tU}{H}, \quad \tilde{T} = \frac{T - T_c}{\Delta T}, \quad \tilde{p} = \frac{p}{U^2}, \quad \tilde{\nabla} = H\tilde{\nabla} \quad (15)$$

By substituting (15) into (11), defining $T_0 = T_c$, and employing some manipulations, the dimensionless form of the governing equation can be obtained [3]:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\nabla} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{u}}}{\partial \tilde{t}} + (\tilde{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \tilde{\nabla})\tilde{\mathbf{u}} &= -\tilde{\nabla}\tilde{p} + \sqrt{\frac{Pr}{Ra}}\tilde{\nabla}^2\tilde{\mathbf{u}} + \tilde{T}\hat{\mathbf{e}}_z - \frac{1}{Ro}\hat{\mathbf{e}}_z \times \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{T}}{\partial \tilde{t}} + (\tilde{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \tilde{\nabla})\tilde{T} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{PrRa}}\tilde{\nabla}^2\tilde{T} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Here Ra is called the Rayleigh number, Pr is the Prandtl number, and Ro is the Rossby number, these commonly used dimensionless numbers were substituted and represented through the following formulas [3]:

$$Ra = \frac{g\alpha_T H^3 \Delta T}{\nu\kappa}, \quad Pr = \frac{\nu}{\kappa}, \quad Ro = \frac{\sqrt{g\alpha_T H\Delta T}}{2\Omega H}. \quad (17)$$

Thereby, the Rayleigh number describes the relationships between buoyancy and viscosity within the fluid, the Prandtl number represents the relationship between momentum diffusivity and thermal diffusivity [23], and the Rossby number measures the relative importance of inertial forces to rotation [20]. In section 1.1 Ekman number Ek was discussed, which provides alternative measures for the effects of rotation on the system, and can be quantified as follows [3]:

$$Ek = \frac{\nu}{2\Omega H^2} \quad (18)$$

It is not an independent quantity, it can be represented through the dimensionless numbers included in the equation (16) as $Ek = Ro\sqrt{\frac{Pr}{Ra}}$ [3]. In this way, unbounded RRBC is described by three independent control parameters [3]. Additionally, the essential output parameter for RRBC is the Nusselt number Nu , quantifying the efficiency of heat transfer due to convection relative to conduction across the fluid layer

[3], [23]. It can be represented as follows:

$$Nu = \frac{qH}{k\Delta T} \quad (19)$$

where q is the total heat flux, and k is the fluid's thermal conductivity [1].

2 Methods

2.1 Simulation method

In this section, the simulation setup and simulating method are discussed. The system is simulated within a rectangular cuboidal computational domain. To mimic horizontally unbounded flow, periodic boundary conditions are applied in both horizontal directions. At the top and bottom of the domain, stress-free, non-permeable boundary conditions and constant temperatures are imposed. These conditions can be represented as follows [3]:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \tilde{u}}{\partial \tilde{z}} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial \tilde{z}} = 0, \quad \tilde{w} = 0, \quad \tilde{T} = 1 \quad \text{at} \quad \tilde{z} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{u}}{\partial \tilde{z}} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial \tilde{z}} = 0, \quad \tilde{w} = 0, \quad \tilde{T} = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad \tilde{z} = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The geometry of the domain is described in the convective units of the length with the length scale H . The dimensions of the domain are the following: the height of the domain H is 1, the periodicity length of the domain in the x -direction (L_x) is 0.8, and the periodicity length in the y -direction (L_y) is varied for this study in the range from 0.8 to 0.896. The principal parameters used for all simulations, if not stated otherwise, are the following: $Ra = 2 \cdot 10^9$, $Ro = 0.0907$, $Pr = 2.19$. These parameters led to the emergence of the flow exhibiting characteristics of the geostrophic turbulence regime of RRBC, within which our study should be conducted.

The domain is discretized using a Cartesian grid, which is uniform in the x and y directions but non-uniform in the z -direction. Velocities are defined at the cell faces corresponding to the lower respective coordinates, while temperature and pressure are defined at the cell centers [3].

The evolution of the flow in both space and time is simulated by numerically solving the equations (16). This is achieved using a finite-difference scheme that is second-order accurate in space and employs a dynamic fractional-step Runge-Kutta method for time-stepping, which is third-order accurate in time [3]. The computational code used for these simulations is implemented in Fortran. This code is an adapted Cartesian version of the original code developed by Verzicco and Orlandi [24] for a cylindrical coordinate system [3]. The initial conditions for the simulations started from the beginning is the velocity field that is zero in all directions and a linear temperature profile from T_h to T_c superimposed by random fluctuations of $O(10^{-2})$ [3].

2.2 Analysis methods to assess the occurrence of the inverse energy cascade

In this section, the analyses performed to assess whether system flow corresponds to the geostrophic turbulence regime of RRBC are discussed. Specifically, for this purpose, two analyses were conducted to provide evidence of the inverse energy cascade occurrence and to demonstrate that energy accumulates at quasi-2D large scales.

To begin, the distribution of kinetic energy with respect to degrees of freedom, as well as the barotropic (vertical axis independent) and baroclinic (vertical axis dependent) energy components, is investigated. As shown in section 1.3.3, it is expected that when the system reaches statistical stability and when it is rotation-dominated, the vertical kinetic energy and baroclinic energy will be very small relative to the barotropic horizontal kinetic energy. The expressions for horizontal barotropic kinetic energy E_{bt} , horizontal baroclinic kinetic energy E_{bc} , vertical kinetic energy E_z , and total kinetic energy E_{tot} were calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{bt} &= \frac{1}{2} \langle \bar{u}^2 + \bar{v}^2 \rangle \\
 E_{bc} &= \frac{1}{2} \langle u'^2 + v'^2 \rangle \\
 E_z &= \frac{1}{2} \langle w^2 \rangle \\
 E_{tot} &= \frac{1}{2} \langle u^2 + v^2 + w^2 \rangle = E_{bt} + E_{bc} + E_z
 \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

Where $\langle \rangle$ brackets denote the average over the entire spatial domain, and bar (for example, \bar{u}) denotes z-averaging; u' and v' are the fluctuating velocity components of the x and y components of the velocity, respectively. Consequently:

$$u' = u - \bar{u} \quad v' = v - \bar{v} \tag{22}$$

In this way, to assess whether energy is mostly distributed in the horizontal depth-independent energy component, the evolution of the energies E_{bt} , E_{bc} , E_z , E_{tot} were plotted over time with the purpose to demonstrate significant E_{bt} growth relative to other energy components as the system reaches energy equilibrium.

Furthermore, as we expect energy to accumulate at the largest scales and be predominantly contained within the horizontal flow, the majority of the energy should reside within large-scale horizontal structures once the system reaches energetic equilibrium. To confirm these characteristics for our system, the kinetic energy spectrum for the height-averaged 2D slabs is computed. For this, first, the 2D Fourier transforms were computed for the slabs of the z-averaged x , y , and z velocity components \hat{u} , \hat{v} and \hat{w} , respectively. Then, the energy contained in each mode was calculated by summing the energy for each specific frequency, determined as the Fourier transform of the two-point correlation of the velocity fluctuations in the slab. In this way, the energy spectrum for the total energy E_{tot} , horizontal energy E_{hor} , and vertical

energy E_{vert} can be found through the following formulas:

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{tot}(k) &= \sum_{k \leq \sqrt{k_x^2 + k_y^2} < k+1} \hat{u}(k) \cdot \hat{u}^*(k) + \hat{v}(k) \cdot \hat{v}^*(k) + \hat{w}(k) \cdot \hat{w}^*(k), \\
E_{hor}(k) &= \sum_{k \leq \sqrt{k_x^2 + k_y^2} < k+1} \hat{u}(k) \cdot \hat{u}^*(k) + \hat{v}(k) \cdot \hat{v}^*(k), \\
E_{vert}(k) &= \sum_{k \leq \sqrt{k_x^2 + k_y^2} < k+1} \hat{w}(k) \cdot \hat{w}^*(k),
\end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

where $\hat{u}(k)$, $\hat{v}(k)$, $\hat{w}(k)$ are the Fourier transforms components that correspond to the specific renormalized wave number $\frac{k}{k_{Lx}}$, where $k = |\mathbf{k}| = \sqrt{k_x^2 + k_y^2}$ and $k_{Lx} = \frac{2\pi}{L_x}$. \hat{u}^* , \hat{v}^* , and \hat{w}^* represent complex conjugates of \hat{u} , \hat{v} and \hat{w} , respectively. The corresponding code can be found in Appendix A.1. Consequently, the wave number k can be coupled to the dimension of the eddy, with small k relating to large scales. In this way, in our analysis, to ensure that horizontal energy accumulates at the largest scales while small scales and vertical energy contributions remain significantly smaller, the energy spectrum for E_{tot} , E_{hor} , and E_{vert} for height-averaged 2D slabs once the system is at energetic equilibrium were computed.

Additionally, in the case of an inverse energy cascade, it is expected that energy will be transferred from the small scales, where it is injected due to the temperature gradient and rotation (horizontal convective size), to the large scales of comparable size to the width of the computational domain [9]. Consequently, before the system reaches energy equilibrium, it is anticipated that energy in large scales will be growing significantly, while small and intermediate scales will facilitate energy transfer and saturate much faster than the largest scale structures, as shown in [9]. To identify features of the following process, the evolution of the energies $E_{tot}(k)$, $E_{hor}(k)$, and $E_{vert}(k)$ of the first 10 modes with time were computed for height-averaged 2D slabs.

2.3 Discerning LSVs and jets

In this section, the analyses performed to identify the coherent large-scale structures of the flow from the examination of the flow behavior is discussed.

To begin, the general qualitative behavior of the flow is analyzed. At this stage, the horizontal kinetic energy E_{2D} and z-component of the vorticity vector ω_z is computed for the vertically averaged velocity field slabs. Additionally, the z-averaged slabs of the u and v velocities components are also plotted. $\overline{E_{2D}}$ and $\overline{\omega_z}$ were calculated according to the definitions:

$$\overline{E_{2D}} = \frac{1}{2} (\overline{u^2} + \overline{v^2}) \quad \overline{\omega_z} = \frac{\partial \overline{v}}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \overline{u}}{\partial y} \tag{24}$$

The corresponding codes are attached in Appendix A.2. The selected quantities are considered relevant for analyses since as mentioned in section 1.3.3 the flow can be treated as z-invariant, with a relatively small vertical velocity component. E_{2D} quantity is expected to highlight the regions of high kinetic

energy belonging to the 2D coherent flow, which is expected to show silhouettes resembling vortex or jets. ω_z is expected to show regions of high vorticity for the large-scale vortex region and identify small-scale vortical structures in the shear regions between jets developed in opposite directions. Slabs of vertically averaged u and v can also give insights into the flow features. While jets are characterized by development in a particular direction, the LSV state can be interpreted as a superposition of jet flows stably developed in both horizontal directions simultaneously [3].

Additionally, the flow behavior was analyzed by computing the instantaneous curves that are everywhere tangent to the direction of the velocity field, commonly known as streamlines [7]. Since the curves of the constant streamfunction represent the streamlines [7], the streamfunction of the flow was calculated first and then the streamlines were plotted as the isolines of the streamfunction. According to the definition of the streamfunction [7]:

$$\bar{u} = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} \quad \bar{v} = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \quad (25)$$

The streamfunction for the 2D velocity field was computed according to the following formula:

$$\psi(x, y) = \int_{y_0}^y \bar{u} dy - \int_{x_0}^x \bar{v} dx, \quad \psi(x_0, y_0) = 0. \quad (26)$$

The integration was performed numerically using the trapezoidal rule. Then the isolines for the computed streamfunction scalar field were plotted. The corresponding codes are included in Appendix A.3.

The analyses performed previously can efficiently capture jets; however, identifying a vortex is more challenging because it is not inherently clear what exactly constitutes a vortex [25]. A vortex is typically regarded as a region that has a vorticity concentration strong enough to induce a local roll-up of the flow and keep a characteristic shape for a reasonable time [20]. While vorticity is a primary criterion for identifying these regions, it is also present in shear-dominated areas of flow. Therefore, a more specific metric is required to accurately identify a vortex. A definition of a vortex from the local flow topology point of view is presented in [26]. This definition suggests that vortex cores should be defined as regions of space with vorticity sufficiently strong to cause the rate-of-strain tensor to be dominated by the rotation tensor [26], [27]. In these regions, the rate-of-deformation tensor must have complex eigenvalues [27]. This definition also is independent of the reference frame of the observer [27]. Building on this concept, Vorobieff and Ecke [27] introduced specific criteria for identifying vortex regions in 2D flow. This involves constructing the rate-of-deformation tensor from the derivatives of horizontal velocity components:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \end{pmatrix}$$

The eigenvalues of the matrix A are complex if the following condition is true:

$$(\text{Tr } A)^2 - 4 \det A < 0 \quad (27)$$

We define Q_{2D} as $Q_{2D} = 4 \det A - (\text{Tr } A)^2$. In this way, Q_{2D} was calculated based on the depth averaged velocity slabs, and utilized in this study to identify regions of a vortex. The corresponding code can be found in Appendix A.4. Notably, this condition is identical to the two-dimensional form of the generally known Q-criterion for identifying vortices, introduced by several authors [25]. They separate the rate-of-deformation tensor into its symmetric part, representing the rate-of-strain tensor, and the non-symmetric part, representing the vorticity tensor. A vortex is defined as a region where the square of the Euclidean norm of the vorticity tensor is larger than the square of the Euclidean norm of the rate-of-strain tensor [25]. Due to the equivalence of the 2D form of Q-criterion and condition (27), this condition is referred to as the Q-criterion in this study. Practically, the threshold value in Q-criterion zero to discern vortices from the surrounding flow was found to be unsuitable due to small fluctuations to the calculated Q_{2D} values due to discretization errors [25]. In our study, to identify an appropriate threshold value for the Q-criterion a method similar to that described in [25] was employed. The suitable threshold was determined by taking the root-mean-square of Q_{2D} calculated for the horizontal cross-section, denoted as Q_{RMS} , and multiplying it by a scaling factor of 0.02. This scaling factor was chosen because it produced relatively convex, smooth regions representing large-scale vortices, while also encompassing the areas of high kinetic 2D energy corresponding to the ring-like structures observed in the z-averaged velocity field slabs. Thereby, in this study vortex was defined as the region of the slab where $Q_{2D} > Q_{RMS}$.

2.4 Order parameter

To quantify the transition between LSVs and jets a concept of an order parameter according to equilibrium statistical mechanics is used. The characteristic quantity α , introduced by Guervilly and Hughes [8], was successfully utilized to distinguish between LSVs and jets in the RRBC simulations conducted in a Cartesian periodic domain [8]. The α is expected to be 0 for LSVs and close to unity for jets. The definition of the parameter α is as follows:

$$\alpha = \frac{\langle u^2 \rangle - \langle v^2 \rangle}{\langle u^2 \rangle + \langle v^2 \rangle} \quad (28)$$

Additionally, this parameter was utilized and modified by de Wit [3], with the purpose of increasing the sensitivity of the parameter by considering only the barotropic 2D velocity field. This modification minimizes the influence of background turbulence. The definition of the modified parameter α_{2D} is the following:

$$\alpha = \frac{\langle \bar{u}^2 \rangle - \langle \bar{v}^2 \rangle}{\langle \bar{u}^2 \rangle + \langle \bar{v}^2 \rangle} \quad (29)$$

The α_{2D} is also expected to be 0 for LSVs and close to unity for jets [3]. For our system, these parameters have shown effectiveness in quantifying LSVs, jets as well as intermediate flow states. Therefore, α and α_{2D} were selected to serve as analogs to order parameters, describing the transition between these flow structures.

2.5 The procedures of the investigation

In this section, the methods to conduct this study are discussed. The study consisted of several stages.

First, the parameters for the simulations, corresponding to the flow regime exhibiting characteristics of geostrophic turbulence, were tuned. For this part of the study, a grid with $N_x = 512$, $N_y = 512$, $N_z = 384$ was selected. The choice of this grid was motivated by research conducted by Yang [28], where simulations in a Cartesian doubly periodic domain with non-slip boundary conditions at the top and bottom for a Prandtl number corresponding to fluids were investigated using the same grid resolution. Three simulations were run with the following parameters: $Ra = 1 \cdot 10^9$, $Ro = 0.0453$, $Pr = 4.38$; $Ra = 1 \cdot 10^9$, $Ro = 0.0641$, $Pr = 2.19$; and $Ra = 2 \cdot 10^9$, $Ro = 0.0907$, $Pr = 2.19$. To check whether the flow exhibited characteristics of quasi-2D behavior and energy growth at the largest scales, the evolution of different energy components with time as well as horizontal kinetic energy snapshots of the horizontal cross-section were analyzed. The specifications of the simulation chosen for further study at this stage were $Ra = 2 \cdot 10^9$, $Ro = 0.0907$, $Pr = 2.19$.

Secondly, the grid resolution was verified for the studied system, with performed analyses discussed in section 2.6.

Next, additional evidence was sought to confirm that selected principal parameters produced the flow regime with an occurrence of inverse energy cascade characteristic to geostrophic turbulence by conducting analyses of section 2.2 for simulation 1 according to table 1. Additionally, for each simulation, the energy spectrum was monitored to ensure it exhibited the shape characteristic to the inverse energy cascade.

Finally, a study to examine the transition characteristics between LSVs to jets was conducted. This involved running 21 simulations with L_y/L_x varying from 1 to 1.12, and analyzing the flow by techniques discussed in sections 2.3 and 2.4. The simulations were initialized in several ways: starting from the beginning with initial conditions described in section 2.1, and from the velocity and temperature fields corresponding to formed LSVs or jets obtained from other simulations in this study. Additionally, to compensate for the elongation of one horizontal side of the domain in simulations with relatively high geometric anisotropy, grid points were added in the y-direction. Specifically, for simulations 19 and 21, the grid resolution was $N_x = 512$, $N_y = 564$, $N_z = 384$. The specifications of all run simulations including information about initial conditions are included in table 1. The simulations were run from 700 to 1800 convective time units depending on when they reached convergence or met partial requirements for convergence. For this study, the simulation run was considered to be converged based on two conditions:

1. The system had to be in energetic equilibrium for at least 300 convective time units. Energetic equilibrium was defined as the state when the cumulative average of the system's barotropic kinetic energy, calculated over 350 convective time units after the system reaches visual equilibrium, remained within a 3% corridor for at least 300 convective time units.
2. The anisotropy parameters α and α_{2D} serving as order parameters in this study and introduced and discussed in 2.4, had to converge. The α and α_{2D} were considered to converge when their cumulative

averages, calculated from the moment the system reached confirmed energetic equilibrium, remained within a 0.01 dimensionless linear units corridor for at least 100 convective time units. An example of the converged α is shown below.

Figure 1: Example of the definition of the convergence for α parameter. The cumulative average of α from the moment when the system is at energetic equilibrium is plotted. The solid black line separates the last 100 convective time units. The corridor is represented by the red dashed lines. For α to be converged the width of the corridor encompassing fluctuations of the cumulative average of α should not be more than 0.01 linear units. This example was plotted for simulation 1 according to table 1 that was run in the square domain.

Simulation Number	L_y/L_x	α_{in}	α_{2Din}	Identified initialization state	Preceding Simulation Number
1	1	-	-	start	none
2	1.01	0.81	0.92	jets	5
3	1.015	0.81	0.92	jets	5
4	1.0175	0.81	0.92	jets	5
5	1.02	0.81	0.94	jets	16
6	1.05	-	-	start	none
7	1.05	0.81	0.94	jets	16
8	1.055	0.19	0.22	LSVs	6
9	1.06	-	-	start	none
10	1.065	0.19	0.22	LSVs	6
11	1.07	-	-	start	none
12	1.07	0.81	0.94	jets	16
13	1.0725	0.19	0.22	LSVs	6
14	1.075	0.19	0.22	LSVs	6
15	1.0775	0.19	0.22	LSVs	6
16	1.08	-	-	start	none
17	1.08	0.19	0.22	LSVs	6
18	1.08	0.22	0.26	LSVs	19
19	1.1	-	-	start	none
20	1.1	0.19	0.22	LSVs	6
21	1.12	0.22	0.26	LSVs	19

Table 1: Table of the simulations specifications. the term “preceding simulation” refers to the simulation from which the 3D velocity and temperature fields were copied and used as initial conditions for the subsequent simulations listed in each row of the table. The variables α_{in} and α_{2Din} quantify the state of the flow configuration in the preceding simulation before it was used as the initial condition for the next simulation. The values of α_{in} and α_{2Din} were calculated using the time average of the α and α_{2D} calculated from the equations (28) and (29), respectively. The averages were taken over 50 convective time units prior to the moment when the 3D velocity fields were transferred to be used as initial conditions for the next simulation. The identified initialization state, which corresponds to a coherent flow structure, was determined by qualitatively assessing the flow behavior through the analyses discussed in Section 2.3.

The degree of convergence for each simulation was monitored and is included in the table 2, section 3.3.

2.6 Grid resolution refinement

The selected grid for x, y, and z directions is $N_x = 512$, $N_y = 512$, $N_z = 384$. As mentioned before, the grid in the x and y directions is uniform, while in the z-direction is non-uniform, with a finer grid closer to the top and bottom of the domain to properly resolve the thermal boundary layer. The ratio of the longest horizontal side to the height of the domain varies between 0.8 and 0.896.

It is crucial to confirm that the flow dynamics within our system remain unaffected by the finite domain width. In our setup, the ratio of the domain width to the height, denoted as Γ , is approximately 11.5 times L_c , where $L_c \approx 4.82Ek^{1/3}$ represents the most unstable wavelength for convective instability [3], [29]. This relation between Γ and L_c is considered sufficient to prevent the domain's geometry from influencing the flow structures [22]. Furthermore, research has demonstrated that such a size of the domain ensures convergence of the Nusselt number [29].

The choice for the grid resolution was motivated by the research done by Yang [28] that investigated the heat transfer and flow structure in RRBC. They used the same grid resolution for simulating RRBC in a horizontally periodic Cartesian domain with non-slip boundary conditions at the top and bottom for $Pr = 4.83$, $Ra = 1 \times 10^9$, $Ro = 0.1$ [28]. For our system, Ro is approximately the same, whereas, Pr is smaller by a factor of 2 and Ra is larger by a factor of 2. Considering that the sufficiency of the grid resolution can be validated by ensuring that the smallest length scale of the flow can be resolved by the selected grid, it is expected that this grid resolution will be suitable for our system since the smallest length scales of the flow in both systems are similar and comparable to the largest grid size. To demonstrate this, the smallest kinematic length scale of the flow in the system, which is well-known Kolmogorov length η , and the smallest length scale of the thermal processes, which is known as Batchelor length η_T , are considered [3]. The respective definitions are as follows [30]:

$$\eta = \left(\frac{v^3}{\epsilon} \right)^{1/4}, \quad \eta_T = \eta \sqrt{\frac{k}{v}}, \quad (30)$$

where ϵ is the dissipation rate of kinetic energy. Then by rescaling the variables into convective units, the smallest length scales can be represented through dimensionless numbers discussed in section 1.3.4, in the following way [21]:

$$\tilde{\eta} = \left(\frac{Pr}{Ra} \right)^{3/8} \tilde{\epsilon}^{-1/4}, \quad \tilde{\eta}_T = \tilde{\eta} Pr^{-1/2}. \quad (31)$$

and the domain-averaged dissipation rates $\langle \epsilon \rangle$ can be represented as follows [21]:

$$\langle \epsilon \rangle = \frac{Nu - 1}{\sqrt{PrRa}}. \quad (32)$$

By estimating the smallest length scale in Yang's research [28] η_1 , η_{T1} and for our system η_2 , η_{T2} , it is found that η_{T2} constitutes 0.75 of the longest grid side length in our system, whereas η_{T1} is smaller than the longest grid side in Yang's system by a factor of 2. This indicates better resolution of the thermal processes in our system than in [28] and thereby indicates grid suitability. Furthermore, η_{T2} is slightly larger than the longest grid side in our system, indicating viability to resolve the smallest kinematic process of the flow.

Next, to properly resolve the thermal boundary layers at the top and bottom of the domain, it was ensured that more than 10 grid cells lie within the boundary layer and that the first grid point is located no further than $\frac{1}{16}$ of the boundary layer thickness from the planes. This follows the minimum resolution

requirement advised by [31]. To determine the thickness of the thermal boundary layer, one traditional approach was employed: identifying the edge of the thermal boundary layer as the maximum of the horizontally and temporally averaged RMS fluctuations of the temperature profile [32]. The formula used to calculate the RMS fluctuations of the temperature profile is $\theta_{RMS} = \sqrt{\langle T^2 \rangle - \langle T \rangle^2}$.

Figure 2: Temporally and spatially averaged temperature profile and RMS fluctuations computed for the simulation in the square domain (simulation 1 according to table 1), the dashed line indicated the edge of the boundary layer determined as maximums of the RMS temperature fluctuations

From Figure 2 it can also be observed that the measured temperature profile provides a reasonable qualitative picture similar to the temperature profiles presented by [32], where the temperature profile was investigated as a function of RRBC principal parameters. This observation further confirms the adequacy of the results and thereby grid resolution.

Furthermore, a grid refinement test was conducted to ensure that the selected grid is appropriate for our study. For this purpose, two additional simulations were run with the same principal parameters, boundary conditions, and an aspect ratio of 0.8 in a square domain, using the following grid resolutions: $N_x = 320$, $N_y = 320$, $N_z = 240$ and $N_x = 640$, $N_y = 640$, $N_z = 480$. To compare the resolution capabilities of the grids the Nusselt number (Nu) was calculated by two methods: by measuring Nu from the direct integration of the convective flux over the volume, and calculated based on the exact relations for the dissipation rates of kinetic energy and thermal variance. The first method will be referred to as method 1, while the latter as method 2 further in this section. Additionally, the standard deviation of the mean temperature profile θ_{RMS} and the shape of the mean temperature profile were compared. The results of the grid refinement tests are presented below.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Coarse grid with $N_x = 320$, $N_y = 320$, $N_z = 240$; normal grid with $N_x = 512$, $N_y = 512$, $N_z = 384$; and fine grid with $N_x = 640$, $N_y = 640$, $N_z = 480$. The ratio $N_x/N_x(normal)$ represents the relationship between the number of grid points for a given simulation and the normal grid simulation. (a) The standard deviation of the mean temperature profile, θ_{RMS} , is computed for the three grid resolutions. (b) The Nusselt number (Nu) is calculated using two methods and averaged over the last 200 convective time units for each grid resolution.

From Figure 3, it can be observed that θ_{RMS} for the three grid resolutions visually overlap. Upon closer inspection, minor discrepancies are apparent, with the coarser grid showing a slightly higher standard deviation at most points. The Nusselt number (Nu) measurements indicate that the selected grid and the two finer grids have significantly narrower gaps compared to the coarser grid, suggesting the reliability of the selected grid. It should also be noted that the simulation for the finer grid was run for 800 convective time units, while the other two simulations were run for nearly 1300 time units. Two methods of measuring Nu typically converge over long time scales (after around 800 convective time units), therefore it might be unreliable to compare the absolute numbers of Nu to the finer grid.

Additionally, for each simulation, the adequacy of the grid was further monitored by ensuring that Nu converged to within a few percent using two different measurement methods discussed above. Since convective flux is highest in regions with large-scale structures and energy dissipation is greatest in regions with small-scale structures, demonstrating convergence of the Nusselt number calculated through these two methods demonstrates convergence at different locations, thereby further confirming adequate spatial resolution. An example of the convergence of Nu measured based on two methods stated above is shown below.

Figure 4: Cumulative average of Nu calculated based on two methods for simulation 1 according to table 1 run in the square domain.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Tuning the principal parameters

Three simulations with different sets of parameters were conducted to optimize the principal parameters of the rotating Rayleigh-Bénard Convection (RRBC) with the goal of achieving the geostrophic turbulence regime. The first two sets of parameters did not result in the desired regime, whereas the third set was successful.

The first attempted set was for $Pr = 4.38$, the horizontal kinetic energy snapshot of a horizontal cross-section as well as the resulted kinetic energy evolution with time are displayed in Figures 5a and 5b, respectively. These results indicate that horizontal kinetic energy does not accumulate significantly at larger scales, displaying only small eddy structures in the snapshot. Furthermore, the evolution of different components of kinetic energy over time reveals that the fraction of horizontal kinetic energy in the system is less than that in isotropic 3D turbulence, suggesting an absence of quasi-2D behavior. This evidence confirmed that the system does not exhibit the geostrophic turbulence regime for this set of parameters.

Julien et al. [32] demonstrated that the existence of the geostrophic turbulence regime is strongly dependent on the Prandtl number. Specifically, given a sufficiently small Ekman number, a higher Rayleigh number is required to achieve the geostrophic turbulence regime at higher Prandtl numbers [32]. However, increasing the Rayleigh number Ra would result in decreased smallest kinematic and thermal process length scales in the flow, as described by the equations (31). Consequently, a higher resolution

would be necessary to solve the system with an increased Ra , which is computationally expensive. To find a less computationally demanding solution, the Prandtl number was reduced to $Pr = 2.19$. The results of the second set of parameters are shown in Figures 5c and 5d. From the horizontal kinetic energy snapshot, it can be observed that energy tends to accumulate at larger scales compared to the first set of parameters. Additionally, the time series of energy evolution shows a higher accumulation of energy than in the first attempt, suggesting that these parameters lead to a state closer to the desired flow regime. However, it can be seen from Figure 5d that vertical kinetic energy $E_{tot} - E_{2D}$ constitutes a significant part of the total energy, indicating no quasi-2D flow behavior.

In the final attempt, it was decided to increase Ra , since this research aimed to focus on Pr valid for liquids, making it not desirable to decrease Pr further. In this way, principal parameters $Ra = 2 \cdot 10^9$, $Ro = 0.0907$, $Pr = 2.19$ were tested. This set exhibited sufficient characteristics of the geostrophic turbulence regime, leading to the conclusion that these parameters correspond to this regime. The analysis confirming this conclusion is discussed in the following section. All subsequent results are based on simulations conducted with the selected principal parameters.

Figure 5: (a),(c) snapshots of E_{2D} for the horizontal cross-section taken at $H/2$ for the runs with parameters $Ra = 1 \cdot 10^9$, $Ro = 0.0453$, $Pr = 4.38$ and $Ra = 1 \cdot 10^9$, $Ro = 0.0641$, $Pr = 2.19$, respectively; (b),(d) evolution of E_{tot} and E_{2D} with time for the runs with parameters $Ra = 1 \cdot 10^9$, $Ro = 0.0453$, $Pr = 4.38$ and $Ra = 1 \cdot 10^9$, $Ro = 0.0641$, $Pr = 2.19$, respectively

3.2 Evidence of the inverse energy cascade occurrence

This section presents and discusses evidence of the occurrence of an inverse energy cascade, thereby demonstrating the emergence of the geostrophic turbulence regime based on simulations conducted in a square domain with the selected principal parameters. Figure 6 illustrates that barotropic horizontal kinetic energy constitutes the majority of the kinetic energy accumulated in the system. In contrast, the baroclinic horizontal and vertical components of kinetic energy are more than ten times smaller than the total kinetic energy. This distribution indicates how rotation influences the system by breaking the isotropy of 3D turbulence and indicating a quasi-2D flow organization.

Figure 6: E_{bt} , E_{bc} , E_z , E_{tot} evolution with time computed for simulation 1 as according to table 1

By analyzing the energy spectrum obtained when the simulation in the square domain reached equilibrium (Figure 7a), it can be observed that the majority of the barotropic kinetic energy is concentrated within the first two wavenumber modes $k = 1, 2$. In contrast, the barotropic energy of the larger modes is of the same order as the vertical kinetic energy, which constitutes a minority as shown in Figure 6. This indicates the accumulation of energy at the largest scales, suggesting the occurrence of an inverse energy cascade. Given the quasi-2D flow organization and energy accumulation at the largest scales, it can be concluded that the system's flow behavior corresponds to the geostrophic turbulence regime.

Interestingly, previous research on the occurrence of the inverse energy cascade for $Pr = 1$ by de Wit [3], Guervilly et al. [9], and Rubio et al. [33] reported that energy accumulated mostly in the first mode. In contrast, our research demonstrates two prominent scales where energy accumulates. From Figure 7b with linear scale it can be observed that once saturation is reached, the second mode contains even more energy than the first mode.

By analyzing the energy evolution over time for different modes (Figure 7b), it can be observed that modes 4-12 reached saturation by 100 convective time units. Mode $k = 3$ saturated after 400 convective time units, reaching a greater amplitude than the larger modes, while the first two modes continued to grow over long time scales. Guervilly et al. [9] reported the saturation of modes $k > 4$ for $t = 50$, which is consistent with our results. However, they also observed the saturation of modes 2-3 by $t = 200$, at a greater amplitude than the higher wavenumbers, exhibiting similar behavior to the mode $k = 3$ in our system.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7: (a) Energy Spectrum of the energy components corresponding to E_{bt} , E_z , $E_{bt} + E_z$ computed for simulation 1 according to table 1 when it reached energetic equilibrium, (b) energy evolution with time for modes 1-12 computed for simulation 1 according to table 1

Furthermore, for this simulation run in the square domain, LSVs were observed (Figure 8). A snapshot of the depth-averaged horizontal kinetic energy for a horizontal cross-section displays regions of relatively high kinetic energy, resembling one LSV with relatively higher kinetic energy and another LSV with relatively weaker kinetic energy (Figure 8a). The Q-criterion analysis confirms that these regions of relatively high kinetic energy indeed correspond to two separate LSVs (Figure 8d). This demonstrates that, as expected, LSVs form for the selected set of parameters. Additionally, Figure 8b shows that horizontal kinetic energy varies very insignificantly along the height of the domain, further demonstrating the quasi-2D organization of the flow.

Figure 8: for simulation 1 according to table 1 initialized from the start and run in domain with $L_y/L_x = 1$. (a) Snapshot of $\overline{E_{2D}}$ for the horizontal cross-section; (b) Snapshot of the y-averaged horizontal kinetic energy $\langle E_{2D} \rangle_y = \frac{1}{2}(\langle u \rangle_y + \langle v \rangle_y)$ for the vertical cross-section; (c) snapshot of axial vorticity $\overline{\omega_z}$ for horizontal cross-section; (d) Q-criterion computed based on the z-averaged horizontal velocity fields for the horizontal cross-section, red indicates regions $Q_{2D} > 0.02Q_{RMS}$, blue corresponds to regions $Q_{2D} \leq 0.02Q_{RMS}$

The occurrence of two LSVs in the square domain is unusual since, as mentioned before, the emergence of one LSV growing to the domain size was reported for $Pr = 1$ [3], [8], [9]. Typically, the LSV configuration includes a strong cyclonic LSV embedded into weaker anticyclonic vorticity [8], [9]. In our case, the snapshot of the depth-averaged axial vorticity shows that the more energetic LSV corresponds to cyclonic rotation with strong circulation, while the less energetic LSV is anticyclonic with weaker circulation, displaying some similarities to the cases for $Pr = 1$ regarding cyclone-anticyclone asymmetry tendencies (Figure 8c). Interestingly, the organization of the flow into two separate cyclonic and anticyclonic LSVs was observed by Aguirre Guzmán et al. [34] in simulations with non-slip bottom and top boundaries for $Pr = 5.2$. This suggests that the difference in flow organization might be linked to the higher Prandtl number of 2.19. Additionally, the occurrence of two prominent modes in our system

might be a result of the formation of two LSVs, signifying that length scales corresponding to half of the box size form quasi-2D coherent structures.

3.3 Results of the examination of non-square domain effects on the flow topology

Results of the temporally averaged order parameters and barotropic kinetic energy as the system reached equilibrium are presented in table 2. Additionally, information about the degree of convergence for each simulation is included.

As predicted, for a sufficient degree of anisotropy in the form of a non-square domain, the emerged flow constituted two quasi-2D jets developing in opposite directions with a shearing region in between characterized by bands of high vorticity (Figures 9a, 9b). All the obtained jets in our simulations formed along the shorter side L_x , as was also observed by Guervilly and Hughes [8] and Julien et al. [13]. They were characterized by coherent parallel flow along L_x and incoherent fluctuating flow along L_y (Figures 9c, 9d). Meanwhile, the LSVs corresponded to the parallel flow developed along L_y and L_x (Figure 10), as was also suggested by de Wit [3].

Figure 9: For simulation 21 according to table 1 initialized from LSVs obtained from the simulation that was initialized naturally in $L_y/L_x = 1.1$ (simulation 19), simulation 21 was run in the domain $L_y/L_x = 1.12$. All quantities are computed for horizontal cross-section: (a) $\overline{E_{2D}}$ barotropic kinetic energy, (b) $\overline{\omega_z}$ axial vorticity. (c) \overline{u} depth-averaged x-velocity component field; (d) \overline{v} depth-averaged y-velocity component field.

(a)

(b)

Figure 10: For simulation 1 according to table 1 initialized from the start and run in domain $L_y/L_x = 1$. The following quantities are computed for horizontal cross-section: (a) \bar{u} depth-averaged x-velocity component field, (b) \bar{v} depth-averaged y-velocity component field.

In our system, at the very early stages, it was noticed that the stability of the LSVs and jets with regard to domain anisotropy are likely to overlap, then the bistability was first observed for the simulation run in domain $L_y/L_x = 1.05$, where LSVs were obtained by initialization from the start and jets remained stable when initializing simulation from the snapshot of jets (simulations 6 and 7 according to table 1). Consequently, the focus was placed on investigating the possibility of hysteresis in the transition region. As expected, analysis of 21 run simulations by utilizing analogs of order parameters α and α_{2D} has shown the hysteresis loop in the transition region between LSVs and jets in Figure 11.

(a)

(b)

Figure 11: Hysteresis loop (a) Order parameter α versus control parameter L_y/L_x . (b) Order parameter α_{2D} versus control parameter L_y/L_x . Red data points correspond to runs that met convergence requirements, blue data points correspond to runs that partially met convergence requirements; labels v, j, and n indicate that a given run was initialized by LSVs or by jets or naturally, respectively. Note v* corresponds to runs that were initialized from LSVs taken from the simulations where afterward (after a long time) the transition to jets occurred. Note * is put near the blue data point corresponding to run $L_y/L_x = 1.0725$, it represents that the corresponding state was obtained by the spontaneous system's fluctuation.

The ascending branch of the hysteresis loop was constructed by initializing most simulations in this branch from snapshots of formed LSVs that were stretched slightly in the y direction. Similarly, the descending branch was built by initializing most simulations in this branch from snapshots of formed jets that were slightly compressed in the y -direction.

Several factors could have affected the accuracy of the demonstrated hysteresis loop. First, when snapshots of jets or LSVs were taken from preceding simulations, the systems were not in energetic equilibrium, and the barotropic kinetic energy was still rising. Furthermore, the state of the LSVs used as snapshots corresponded to $\alpha = 0.19, 0.22$, $\alpha_{2D} = 0.22, 0.26$, while for the square case when the system reached energetic equilibrium, the parameters corresponded to $\alpha = 0.0775$, $\alpha_{2D} = 0.0874$. This could affect the shape of the ascending branch of the hysteresis loop, by causing the system to enter states within the hysteresis loop rather than building an ascending branch for the major hysteresis loop that would display the bounds of the system's states of existence. Additionally, when the snapshots of LSVs or jets were transferred to domains with different geometries, they were slightly stretched or compressed in the y -direction, which could introduce some noise. Given that the turbulent state is unstable to small perturbations, this defect could have affected the results by introducing additional instabilities.

In the following sections, the transition from LSVs to jets and from jets to LSVs will be discussed in detail. Finally, the obtained findings will be compared to previous research.

Sim. Number	L_y/L_x	α	α_{2D}	d_α	$d_{\alpha_{2D}}$	E_{bt}	$d_{E_{bt}}$ in %	t_{eq} $t/(U^{-1}H)$
1	1	0.0775	0.0874	0.0068	0.0077	0.0046	0.43	380
2	1.01	0.0958	0.1078	0.0076	0.0085	0.0048	2.49	350
3	1.015	0.1128	0.1268	0.0054	0.0058	0.0046	1.95	300
4	1.0175	0.0839	0.0945	0.0052	0.0062	0.0046	1.24	500
5	1.02	0.8192	0.9216	0.0047	0.005	0.0039	2.00	350
6	1.05	0.1433	0.1605	0.0049	0.0056	0.0047	0.53	350
7	1.05	0.8424	0.9470	0.0041	0.0039	0.0039	1.43	380
8	1.055	0.1683	0.1888	0.0053	0.0059	0.0047	2.18	320
9	1.06	0.1705	0.1914	0.0064	0.0071	0.0048	1.05	300
10	1.065	0.2074	0.2303	0.0045	0.0051	0.0049	0.57	410
11	1.07	0.2885	0.3232	0.0088	0.0088	0.0049	2.01	300
12	1.07	0.8373	0.9398	0.0051	0.0045	0.0041	2.65	550
13	1.0725	0.3749	0.4151	0.0143	0.0154	0.0050	1.31	300
14	1.075	0.3823	0.4242	0.0067	0.0070	0.0051	1.86	300
15	1.0775	0.2609	0.2916	0.0079	0.0089	0.0049	1.72	300
16	1.08	0.8523	0.9618	0.0063	0.0033	-	-	-
17	1.08	0.3207	0.3601	0.0064	0.0077	0.0048	2.49	300
18	1.08	0.6776	0.7443	0.0034	0.0034	0.0053	2.93	320
19	1.1	0.8549	0.9522	0.0063	0.0059	0.0046	4.38	300
20	1.1	0.8647	0.9592	0.0058	0.0051	0.0045	1.06	300
21	1.12	0.8753	0.9609	0.0052	0.0046	0.0052	1.74	330

Table 2: Order parameters and barotropic kinetic energy results for all runs. Also, the convergence degree for all simulations is presented and calculated as described in section 2.5. d_α and $d_{\alpha_{2D}}$ are the corridor widths within which values of the cumulative averages of α and α_{2D} calculated over 100 convective time units stayed within. The illustration (Figure 1) and details of the procedure of selecting a region of 100 convective time units can be found in 2.5. t_{eq} is regarded as the time during which the cumulative average of the barotropic kinetic energy stayed within the corridor of width $d_{E_{bt}}$ given in the table. For simulation 16 quantities related to the barotropic kinetic energy are not displayed since E_{bt} was growing significantly, and the simulation was not run for long enough due to data loss

3.3.1 Transition from jets to large-scale vortices

Analysis of the transition from jets to LSVs by examining the evolution of the descending branch of the hysteresis loop in terms of the order parameter (Figure 11), shows α and α_{2D} change drastically between runs for $L_y/L_x = 1.02$ and $L_y/L_x = 1.0175$. Likewise, the flow topology has changed drastically, while $L_y/L_x = 1.02$ corresponds to jets-only state, $L_y/L_x = 1.0175$ gives LSVs (Figure 12). Such drastic changes in order parameters and qualitative features of the flow suggest that the transition might be discontinuous. However, more data points are needed in-between $L_y/L_x = 1.02$ and $L_y/L_x = 1.0175$ to support this suggestion.

(a)

(b)

Figure 12: $\overline{E_{2D}}$ computed for the horizontal cross-section: (a) for simulation 5 according to table 1 run in the domain $L_y/L_x = 1.02$, which was initialized from the snapshot of jets obtained from simulation 16 that was run in $L_y/L_x = 1.08$ and initialized from the start ; (b) for the simulation 4 according to table 1 for $L_y/L_x = 1.0175$, which was initialized from the snapshot of jets obtained from simulation 5.

Figure 13 demonstrates how the transition happened in terms of the order parameters evolution with time once the snapshot of jets taken from domain $L_y/L_x = 1.02$ was transferred to domain $L_y/L_x = 1.0175$. It can be observed that transition happens relatively fast, and does not exhibit any intermediate states.

Figure 13: The evolution of α and α_{2D} parameters with time. The first region ($0 < t < 500$) corresponds to simulation 16 according to table 1 for $L_y/L_x = 1.08$ that was initialized from the start. Then the snapshot of jets from simulation 16 was transferred to domain with $L_y/L_x = 1.02$ (simulation 5), corresponding to the second region ($500 < t < 900$). Finally, the snapshot of jets from simulation 5 was transferred to domain with $L_y/L_x = 1.0175$ corresponding to the third region ($900 < t < 1800$) (simulation 4).

The evolution of α and α_{2D} parameters for this transition can be interpreted as if the jets equilibrium state ceases to exist or becomes unstable for $L_y/L_x < 1.02$, and upon decreasing the control parameter, the only one stable equilibrium that exists corresponds to LSVs, thereby the discontinuous jump happens from the upper to lower branch when L_y/L_x decreases below the critical value. This behavior qualitatively resembles the left part of the subcritical pitchfork bifurcation stabilized by higher order terms (Figure 14) [35], which is related to the discontinuous transition in statistical mechanics. Interestingly, once the system transitions to LSVs upon increasing the control parameter, it is unlikely to revert back to jets. Instead, it tends to move along the stable lower branch. This demonstrates a lack of reversibility as the parameter is varied, signifying hysteresis.

Figure 14: Subcritical pitchfork bifurcation stabilized by higher order terms; the solid lines correspond to stable fixed points corresponding to equilibrium points, and broken line corresponds to unstable ones [35]

An interesting characteristic that was spotted during the transition is the visible increase in barotropic kinetic energy as the system transitions from jets to LSVs (Figure 15). This phenomenon was observed for all cases when LSVs transitioned to jets (simulations corresponding to domain $L_y/L_x = 1.01, 1.015, 1.0175$). By assessing the plots of energy evolution visually, it can be observed that the rate of barotropic energy growth is the highest when the system rapidly transitions to jets. Then energy increases at a slightly lower rate while LSVs are saturating. This observation may suggest that LSVs require higher energy accumulation in the system for formation than jets.

Figure 15: (a, b) Correspond to simulation 2 according to table 1 with $L_y/L_x = 1.01$, which was initialized from the jets that were obtained from simulation 5 run in the domain $L_y/L_x = 1.02$. (c,d) Correspond to simulation 3 according to table 1 with $L_y/L_x = 1.015$, which was initialized in the same way as simulation 2. (a, c) Display respective energy components evolution. (b, d) Display respective α and α_{2D} evolution with time. For all plots first region ($0 < t < 500$) represents the system's evolution corresponding to simulation 16, which was run in domain $L_y/L_x = 1.08$. Then the snapshot of jets from simulation 16 was transferred to domain with $L_y/L_x = 1.02$ corresponding to the second region ($500 < t < 900$), third region after the second black line corresponds to domains $L_y/L_x = 1.01$ ($900 < t < 1650$) and $L_y/L_x = 1.05$ ($900 < t < 1600$), respectively. The cyan vertical line corresponds to the moment when the flow topology first corresponded to LSVs.

3.3.2 Transition from large-scale vortices to jets

Assessing the transition from LSVs to jets by analyzing the evolution of the ascending branch of the hysteresis loop in terms of order parameter, Figure 11 demonstrates that α and α_{2D} changes in a continuous manner, by displaying intermediate states between LSVs-only state (corresponding to order parameter of around 0.1-0.2) and jets-only state (corresponding to order parameter of around 0.8 to 1) with a visible tendency of exhibiting higher values of order parameter for higher values of the control

parameter L_y/L_x . This evolution of the order parameters is consistent with qualitative changes in flow organization. The flow organization for simulations started from the snapshot of LSVs for domains with different L_y/L_x is presented in the form of streamlines of z-averaged flow taken at a time when instantaneous α and α_{2D} were the closest to the converged value (Figure 16). From Figure 16 it can be observed how the streamlines changed as the anisotropy increased. The case for $L_y/L_x = 1$ is displayed for the reference, demonstrating vortices consisting of closed streamlines. In contrast, cases for domains $L_y/L_x = 1.055$, $L_y/L_x = 1.065$ show LSVs with around 3 not closed streamlines around them, this could suggest signs of initial stages of parallel flows development in-between LSVs. As anisotropy increases for cases $L_y/L_x = 1.08$, $L_y/L_x = 1.0775$ the number of not closed streamlines increases, resembling banded flows within LSVs. For the case $L_y/L_x = 1.075$, the banded parallel flow is coherent, resembling banded jets embedding LSVs. These gradual qualitative changes in the flow organization, further suggest the occurrence of the continuous transition. However, to be more confident in this conclusion, it is necessary to have more data points between $L_y/L_x = 1.08$ and $L_y/L_x = 1.1$. From the gradual changes in flow topology as well as the order parameters, it can be hypothesized that along the ascending branch, the stable equilibrium becomes unstable or ceases to exist as the control parameter changes. Meanwhile, a new stable equilibrium emerges.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Figure 16: Snapshots of the streamlines computed for the z -averaged velocity fields for the horizontal cross-sections (a) simulation 1 ($L_y/L_x = 1$) (b) simulation 8 ($L_y/L_x = 1.055$), (c) simulation 10 ($L_y/L_x = 1.065$), (d) simulation 14 ($L_y/L_x = 1.075$), (e) simulation 15 ($L_y/L_x = 1.0775$), (d) simulation 17 ($L_y/L_x = 1.08$); simulations numbers are noted as per table 1. All situations except from simulation 1 were initialized from the snapshot of LSVs obtained from simulation 6 that was run in $L_y/L_x = 1.05$ domain.

Interestingly, for simulations run in domains $L_y/L_x = 1.0725$ and $L_y/L_x = 1.0775$ the system spontaneously fluctuated from the state of LSVs with banded flows to the jets state (in case of $L_y/L_x = 1.0775$ started rising to the jets state) (Figure 17). The fluctuations are inherent to turbulent states, thereby it can be expected that for any simulation the system can transition to some state within the hysteresis loop boundaries. However, it can be observed that such spontaneous transitions have not occurred for other control parameters, meanwhile parameters $L_y/L_x = 1.0725$ and $L_y/L_x = 1.0775$ are close to each other, and for both of them for long time α and α_{2D} ceased to converge. This might suggest, relatively low stability of the LSVs with jets-like flow states for these control parameters.

Figure 17: The evolution of the α and α_{2D} parameters with time; (a) corresponds to simulations 13 with $L_y/L_x = 1.0725$; (b) corresponds to simulations 15 with $L_y/L_x = 1.0775$; simulations are referred according to table 1. Both simulations were initialized from LSVs that were obtained from simulation 6 which was initialized from the start

Intriguingly, the transition from LSVs to jets was also associated with consistent changes in barotropic kinetic energy. For all cases where the transition occurs, specifically, for $L_y/L_x = 1.1, 1.2$, the decrease in barotropic kinetic energy was observed when jets state was stabilizing (Figure 18). Interestingly, when the transition was occurring the energy was rising, and the peak region of the barotropic kinetic energy corresponds to the moment when the jets configuration was first reached. The cyan line on the plots reflects the approximate moment when jets configuration was first reached (Figure 18).

Figure 18: (a, b) correspond to simulation 20 according to table 1 with $L_y/L_x = 1.1$, which was initialized from the LSVs obtained from simulation 6 that was run in the domain $L_y/L_x = 1.05$ and was initialized from the start. The first region from the left ($0 < t < 550$) corresponds to the part of the run for simulation 6. Then the snapshot of LSVs was transferred from simulation 6 to domain $L_y/L_x = 1.1$ corresponding to the right side from the vertical line ($550 < t < 1600$). (c,d) Correspond to simulation 21 according to table 1 with $L_y/L_x = 1.12$, which was initialized from LSVs obtained from the part of simulation 19 that was run in $L_y/L_x = 1.1$ domain, and was initialized from the start. The region on the left from the vertical black line ($0 < t < 400$) corresponds to the part of the run for simulation 19. Then the snapshot of LSVs from simulation 19 was transferred to domain $L_y/L_x = 1.12$ corresponding to the right side from the vertical line ($400 < t < 1600$). (a, c) Display respective energy components evolution with time. (b, d) Display respective α and α_{2D} evolution with time. For all plots, cyan vertical line corresponds to the moment when the flow topology first corresponded to jets.

3.3.3 Regions of jets and LSVs stability

The obtained evolution of the order parameter versus the control parameter indicates the occurrence of a hysteresis loop. According to Visintin [36], it is typically reasonable to assume that any point within the region bounded by the hysteresis loop is accessible to any pair of order and control parameters. This

argument is supported by the idea that, for a controllable system, a suitable choice of the function of the control parameter can drive the system from any initial point to any final point within the hysteresis region [36]. In our system, there were cases that belonged to the region lying within the hysteresis loop. It is challenging to determine where the simulations were naturally initialized, but the order parameter for simulation 11 with $L_y/L_x = 1.07$ seems to belong to the inner region, as it visually lies above the ascending branch trend. Additionally, a couple of cases were run from the initial conditions corresponding to LSVs of relatively high $\alpha = 0.22$ and $\alpha_{2D} = 0.26$ parameters, mainly for simulations 18 corresponding to $L_y/L_x = 1.08$ and simulation 21 with $L_y/L_x = 1.12$. In simulation 21, the flow emerged into jets, which was expected since this case belongs to the region where only one stable equilibrium, corresponding to jets, is anticipated. Meanwhile, simulation 18 emerged into a mixed state characterized by jets with relatively high kinetic energy and less energetic LSVs that could still be captured by the Q-criterion (Figure 19). This case can be stated to correspond to the inner region of the hysteresis loop, as simulation 17, with the same control parameter, was run from a snapshot of LSVs corresponding to lower values of the order parameter.

Figure 19: Results computed for simulation 18 in the domain $L_y/L_x = 1.08$, which was initialized from LSVs obtained from simulation 19 that was initialized from the start and run in the domain $L_y/L_x = 1.08$; (a) evolution of α and α_{2D} parameters with time, the region on the left from the vertical black line corresponds to the part of the run for simulation 19 for $L_y/L_x = 1.1$, that has been transferred to domain $L_y/L_x = 1.08$ corresponding to the right side from the vertical line; (b) $\overline{E_{2D}}$ depth-average horizontal kinetic energy for the horizontal cross-section; (c) streamlines computed based on the z-averaged velocity fields for the horizontal cross-section; (d) Q-criterion computed for horizontal cross-section, red indicates regions $Q_{2D} > 0.02Q_{RMS}$, blue corresponds to regions $Q_{2D} \leq 0.02Q_{RMS}$

From our investigation, it can be concluded that an only-jets state exists for the domain geometry corresponding to $L_y/L_x \in [1.02; 1.12]$. In contrast, investigations of non-square domain effects on the 3D flow in the geostrophic turbulence regime for $Pr = 1$ reported a minimum domain anisotropy for where jets can exist of $L_y/L_x = 1.06$ for $Ek = 10^{-4}$, and $L_y/L_x = 1.08$ for $Ek = 10^{-5}$ [8], which is larger but of the same order as ours. This suggests that for $Pr = 2.19$, the jet flow configuration is less sensitive to domain anisotropy than for $Pr = 1$.

Interestingly, Guervilly and Hughes [8], Julien et al. [13], and Frishman et al. [14] reported that LSVs persistently coexisted with jets. Even in highly anisotropic domains, LSVs were still observed [8], [13], [14]. In our case, the state of LSVs with jets was obtained for the narrow range of approximately $L_y/L_x \in [1.0725; 1.08]$ and is reasonably expected to exist for $L_y/L_x \in [1.02; 1.1]$. Frishman et al. [14] suggested that the presence of LSVs in addition to jets occurs due to the locally induced inverse energy cascade that tends to create vortices, while the domain’s anisotropy is only felt when their size of a vortex is comparable to L_x . Based on this mechanism, it can be hypothesized that for $Pr = 2.19$, the effects of the locally induced inverse energy cascade are inhibited, possibly due to lower momentum diffusivity related to the higher Prandtl number or higher inertia within the main flow, leading to a preference for an only-jets state.

Interestingly, our study identifies a region of multistability for $L_y/L_x \in [1.02, 1.1]$. In contrast, Guervilly and Hughes [8] reported bistability within the region $L_y/L_x \in [1.06, 1.15]$. Their findings indicate that for $Pr = 1$, the LSVs-only configuration can exist at higher degrees of anisotropy compared to $Pr = 2.19$. This suggests that for $Pr = 1$, LSVs may be less sensitive to the domain geometry. Furthermore, Bouchet and Simonnet [15], in their simulations of 2D forced turbulence, reported bistability for $L_y/L_x \in [1.02, 1.04]$. This result aligns closely with our findings, as the boundary for the existence of jets coincides. Additionally, for anisotropy values greater than 1.04, LSVs tend to exhibit characteristics of jet flows.

4 Conclusion and Future Research

This research explored the transition between large-scale vortices (LSVs) and jets in 3D rotating Rayleigh-Bénard convection (RRBC), simulated with periodic boundary conditions in both horizontal directions and stress-free top and bottom boundaries, for $Ra = 2 \cdot 10^9$, $Pr = 2.19$, and $Ro = 0.0907$. The investigated RRBC regime corresponded to geostrophic turbulence. The study examined the transition between flow organizations as the ratio between the horizontal sides of the computational domain, L_y/L_x , exceeded unity.

The investigation proceeded in three steps. First, RRBC parameters (Ra , Pr , and Ro) were tuned to achieve flow characteristics consistent with the geostrophic turbulence regime. Additional analysis confirmed a quasi-2D organization of the flow and energy accumulation at the largest scales, suggesting an inverse energy cascade typical of geostrophic turbulence. Next, 21 simulations were conducted for $L_y/L_x \in [1; 1.12]$, initialized from either stationary fields with perturbations, or LSVs or jets snapshots. The transition was analyzed using order parameters to quantify flow anisotropy and by qualitatively assessing flow configurations.

The results indicated a hysteresis loop in the transition region $L_y/L_x \in [1.02; 1.1]$. The ascending branch corresponded to the transition from LSVs to jets, while the descending branch described the transition from jets to LSVs. Although the data were insufficient to definitively identify transition types,

some signs were observed. The ascending branch exhibited characteristics of a continuous transition, with gradual changes in order parameters and flow configuration, evolving from LSVs to LSVs with banded jets, and finally to jets as L_y/L_x increased. In contrast, the descending branch showed characteristics of a discontinuous transition, with abrupt changes in order parameters and flow configuration, transitioning directly from jets to LSVs upon a slight decrease in L_y/L_x .

Several potential defects in this research could have affected the accuracy of the results. First, the LSVs and jets in the initial condition snapshots were not at energetic equilibrium. Second, transferring snapshots between domains of different geometries required compression or stretching, which could introduce noise and affect the turbulent system. Finally, the LSVs snapshots did not match the order parameters characteristic of LSVs in symmetrical domains, potentially impacting the boundaries of the ascending branch.

Previous research investigated this transition for $Pr = 1$ [8], [13]. The observed hysteresis in our study aligns with previous findings, as studies by Guervilly and Hughes [8] and Bouchet and Simonnet [15] reported bistability in the transition region. However, the critical values of L_y/L_x differed, with jets being stable at lower L_y/L_x values in our study. Additionally, for $Pr = 1$, the characteristic flow configuration in sufficiently anisotropic domains included jets with embedded LSVs [8], [13], whereas, in our study, the jets-only flow was observed as the upper bound of the hysteresis loop.

Moreover, while previous studies noted that the flow in a square domain for $Pr = 1$ usually comprised a domain-filling cyclonic vortex embedded within an anticyclonic vorticity background [8], [9], our study identified the flow in the square domain as consisting of two LSVs with distinct cyclonic and anticyclonic vorticities.

Furthermore, we observed two prominent wavenumbers, corresponding to modes $k = 1, 2$, which contained the majority of the barotropic kinetic energy. This contrasts with earlier research that reported one prominent mode ($k = 1$) as the inverse energy cascade occurs [9].

Interestingly, it was also observed that the depth-independent horizontal kinetic energy consistently increased during the transition from jets to LSVs, and decreased during the transition from LSVs to jets. This suggests that the formation of LSVs requires a higher accumulation of barotropic kinetic energy compared to jets.

Regarding further research, it is beneficial to conduct additional simulations using initial conditions that correspond to LSVs-only or jets-only states at energetic equilibrium. This approach would enable a more accurate identification of the nature of the transition. Furthermore, given the characteristic barotropic kinetic energy accumulation associated with jets and LSVs, it would be valuable to assess the transition in terms of barotropic kinetic energy accumulation.

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A Appendix

A.1 Computing Energy Spectrum

```
1 function [k_axis, E, E_hor, E_vert] = energySpectrum(u, v, w)
2
3 arguments (Input)
4     u (:,:) double
5     v (:,:) double
6     w (:,:) double
7 end
8
9 arguments (Output)
10    k_axis (:,1) double
11    E (:,1) double
12    E_hor (:,1) double
13    E_vert (:,1) double
14 end
15
16 [nx, ny] = size(u);
17
18 U = fftshift(fft2(u));
19 V = fftshift(fft2(v));
20 W = fftshift(fft2(w));
21
22 E = zeros(nx-1,1);
23 E_hor = zeros(nx-1,1);
24 E_vert = zeros(nx-1,1);
25
26 for i = 1:nx
27     for j = 1:ny
28         k = floor(sqrt((i - nx/2)^2 + (j - ny/2)^2));
29         if k>0
30             if k<nx
31                 E_hor(k) = E_hor(k) + V(i,j)*conj(V(i,j)) + U(i,j)*conj(U(i,j));
32                 E_vert(k) = E_vert(k) + W(i,j)*conj(W(i,j));
33                 E(k) = E(k) + V(i,j)*conj(V(i,j)) + U(i,j)*conj(U(i,j)) ...
34                     + W(i,j)*conj(W(i,j));
35             end
36         end
37     end
38 end
39
40 k_axis = 1:1:(nx-1);
41 end
```

A.2 Computing depth-averaged horizontal kinetic energy $\overline{E_{2D}}$ and z-averaged axial vorticity $\overline{\omega_z}$

```
1 function [E_2D, Vort_z] = horizontalEnergyAndAxialVorticity(u, v, L_x, L_y)
2
3 arguments (Input)
4     u (:,:) double
5     v (:,:) double
6     L_x (1,1) double
7     L_y (1,1) double
8 end
9
10 arguments (Output)
11     E_2D (:,:) double
12     Vort_z (:,:) double
13 end
14
15 % 2D energy
16 E_2D = u.^2 + v.^2;
17
18 %axial vorticity
19 [nx, ny] = size(u);
20 Vort_z = zeros(nx, ny);
21
22 u(:,ny+1) = u(:,1);
23 u(nx+1,:) = u(1,:);
24 v(:,ny+1) = v(:,1);
25 v(nx+1,:) = v(1,:);
26
27 lx = L_x/nx;
28 ly = L_y/ny;
29
30 for i = 1:nx
31     for j = 1:ny
32         Vort_z(i, j) = (v(i+1, j+1) - v(i, j+1))/lx - (u(i+1, j+1) - u(i+1, j))/ly;
33     end
34 end
35 end
```

A.3 Computing streamlines

```
1 function contourMap = streamlinesMap(u, v, L_x, L_y, Resolution)
2
3 arguments (Input)
4     u (:,:) double
5     v (:,:) double
6     L_x (1,1) double
7     L_y (1,1) double
8     Resolution (1,1) double
9 end
10
11 arguments (Output)
12     contourMap
13 end
14
15 [nx, ny] = size(u);
16
17 lx = L_x/nx;
18 ly = L_y/ny;
19
20 PSI = zeros(nx, ny);
21
22 for i = nx: -1: 1
23     if (i == nx)
24         PSI(i, nx) = 0;
25     else
26         PSI(i, ny) = PSI(i+1, ny) + (lx*(v(i+1, ny) + v(i, ny)))/2);
27     end
28
29     for j = (ny-1): -1: 1
30         PSI(i, j) = PSI(i, j+1) - (ly*(u(i, j+1) + u(i, j)))/2);
31     end
32 end
33
34 contourMap = contour(PSI, Resolution);
35 ax = gca;
36 ax.XTick = [];
37 ax.YTick = [];
38 ax.TickLength = [0 0];
39
40 end
```

A.4 Computation Q-criterion

```
1 function [Q_criterion,VortexIdentification] ...
2 = vortexIdentification(u,v, L_x, L_y, noiseFilteringCoefficient)
3
4 arguments (Input)
5     u (:,:) double
6     v (:,:) double
7     L_x (1,1) double
8     L_y (1,1) double
9     noiseFilteringCoefficient (1,1) double
10 end
11
12 arguments (Output)
13     Q_criterion (:,:) double
14     VortexIdentification (:,:) double
15 end
16
17 [nx, ny] = size(u);
18
19 lx = L_x/nx;
20 ly = L_y/ny;
21
22 u(:,ny+1) = u(:,1);
23 u(:,ny+2) = u(:,2);
24 u(nx+1,:) = u(1,:);
25 u(nx+2,:) = u(2,:);
26 v(:,ny+1) = v(:,1);
27 v(:,ny+2) = v(:,2);
28 v(nx+1,:) = v(1,:);
29 v(nx+2,:) = v(2,:);
30
31 Q_criterion = zeros(nx, ny);
32 U_tensor = zeros(2);
33 VortexIdentification = zeros(nx, ny);
34
35 for i = 1:nx
36     for j = 1:ny
37         u2 = u(i+2, j) + (u(i+2, j+1) - u(i+2, j))/2;
38         u1 = u(i, j) + (u(i, j+1) - u(i, j))/2;
39         U_tensor(1, 1) = (u2 - u1)/(2*lx);
40         v2 = v(i, j+2) + (v(i+1, j+2) - v(i, j+2))/2;
41         v1 = v(i, j) + (v(i+1, j) - v(i, j))/2;
42         U_tensor(2, 2) = (v2 - v1)/(2*ly);
43         U_tensor(1, 2) = (u(i+1, j+1) - u(i+1, j))/(ly);
44         U_tensor(2, 1) = (v(i+1, j+1) - v(i, j+1))/(lx);
```

```
45
46     Q_criterion(i, j) = 4*det(U_tensor) - (trace(U_tensor)^2);
47 end
48 end
49
50 Q_criterion_RMS = sqrt(mean(Q_criterion.^2, 'all'));
51
52 for i = 1:nx
53     for j = 1:ny
54         if Q_criterion(i, j) > noiseFilteringCoefficient * Q_criterion_RMS
55             VortexIdentification(i,j) = 1;
56         end
57     end
58 end
59 end
```
